

iodine def

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Research Article

Iodine Deficiency and its Association with Periodontitis: A Randomized Controlled Three-Blinded Clinic Study

BACKGROUND

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), micronutrients are essential in very small quantities (measured in micrograms or milligrams per day) and act as "magical tools" that support the production of enzymes, hormones, and other substances necessary for the body's healthy growth and development.¹ Micronutrients, which include essential vitamins and minerals, are crucial for promoting proper metabolic function, facilitating wound healing, and preventing diseases and infections.² *In-vitro* studies have demonstrated that vitamins and trace elements have a significant impact on every aspect of immune function, and a lack of these nutrients can result in compromised immune function.³

Major minerals such as sodium (Na), potassium (K), calcium (Ca), magnesium (Mg), phosphorus (P), and sulfur (S) are required in amounts greater than 100 mg/day, while trace minerals such as iron (Fe), zinc (Zn), selenium (Se), copper (Cu), iodine (I), fluoride (F), cobalt (Co), chromium (Cr), manganese (Mn), and molybdenum (Mo) are required in amounts less than 100 mg/day.⁴ According to reports, deficiencies in micronutrients have been described as a "silent epidemic" affecting individuals of all ages and genders worldwide, impacting approximately 2 billion people globally.⁵ According to the WHO, there are micronutrient deficiencies in several Middle Eastern countries, especially among children and women of childbearing age, involving Ca, Fe, zinc, vitamin A, vitamin D, and folic acid. Iron deficiency is prevalent among a majority of women in these countries, and over 13.2 million preschool children have retinol serum levels below 0.7 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, with approximately 800,000 of them experiencing night blindness.⁶

Nutrients are crucial for preserving the health of the human body and all metabolically active tissues. They also have a critical role in the regeneration process, managing oxidative stress, and maintaining adequate immunity.⁷ While ample data support the significance of vitamins and major minerals in periodontal and overall health, there is limited evidence supporting the functions of trace minerals. Inadequate intake of trace minerals could increase the risk of

1 periodontal disease, either by exacerbating the infection caused by periodontopathogens or by influencing the biological gradients and hemostasis of the host.⁸

30 Periodontitis is a disease with multiple causes that results from intricate interactions between the dental plaque biofilm and the host's immunological inflammatory response. Apart from that, several risk factors related to the environment and the host are believed to contribute significantly to the disease's development. These factors may alter the host's response and the course of the disease.⁹ Several approaches have been employed to slow the progression of periodontitis. Alongside conventional periodontal therapies, 16 various host-modulating agents have been utilized to elicit a favorable host response. These agents include dietary components such as omega-3 fatty acids and micronutrients such as dietary minerals (e.g., Fe, Zn, Se, Cu) and vitamins (A, B complex, C, D, and E) that possess immunomodulatory properties. They aid in preventing infections and regulating inflammation. Moreover, trace minerals impact periodontal health by acting locally on hard and soft tissues and systemically on immune-inflammatory mechanisms.¹⁰

20 Iodine, with an atomic weight of 126.9 g per atom, is a crucial component of thyroid gland hormones, which are essential for mammals. Although widely present in the Earth's environment, iodine is 3 unevenly distributed, with the oceans containing the highest amount of iodide (approximately 50 µg/L). Iodide ions in seawater oxidize into elemental iodine, which is volatile, evaporates into the atmosphere and returns to the soil with rain, thus completing the cycle. However, in many regions, the iodine cycle is slow and incomplete, resulting in iodine-deficient soils and groundwater. 18 Crops grown in these soils have low iodine concentrations, leading to iodine deficiency in humans and animals that consume these crops.¹¹

Studies have demonstrated that iodine possesses an antioxidant function in various tissues, including the breast.¹²⁻¹⁴ In the presence of hydrogen peroxide, iodide can serve as an electron donor, which may reduce the harm caused by oxygen free radicals.¹⁵ Iodide is capable of efficiently eliminating reactive oxygen species (ROS) within human blood cells.¹⁴ Iodine also appears to have a direct association with acute-phase proteins and is utilized by other cells, including immune system cells and liver cells.^{16,17} In addition to its antioxidant properties, iodine has been found to possess anti-inflammatory effects. While the levels of C-Reactive protein (CRP) and Interleukin-6 (IL-6) remained constant after administering different doses 17

of iodide, negative correlations were observed between CRP and free tetraiodothyronine (FT4), as well as urinary iodine and free triiodothyronine (FT3) and IL-6, indicating a link between iodide, thyroid hormone production, and inflammatory status as assessed by CRP and IL-6.¹⁸

OBJECTIVES

While several studies have explored the impact of trace elements, such as Fe, Zn, Se, and Cu, on periodontal health, the current study is unique in its emphasis on the significance between iodine, a trace element, and periodontal health.

The hypothesis of the study and the primary outcome is that the urinary iodine content of patients with periodontitis differs from that of periodontally healthy individuals.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design

The present cross-sectional study included a total of 73 participants referred by the Dentistry of XXX University, Department of Periodontology in 2022. The participants were systemically healthy and non-smoking, consisting of 33 periodontally healthy control subjects and 40 patients with stage III periodontitis (P). All participants were provided with information about the study and signed an informed consent form. The study protocol was approved by the Clinical Research Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Medicine, XXX University (2021/11), and the Clinical Trials ID is "NCT05724251". The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki.

Settings and Division of Patients into Groups

To be eligible for participation in this study, individuals were required to have no systemic illnesses or conditions {such as hepatic or renal dysfunction, diabetes, organ transplantation or cancer therapy, cardiovascular disease, pregnancy or lactation, goiter, hyper or hypothyroidism, or unbalanced thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) levels} and to be in good systemic health. Individuals who had previously been treated for periodontal disease and required antibiotics for infective endocarditis prophylaxis during dental procedures were excluded. Individuals who had previously been treated for periodontal disease were also excluded. Additionally, subjects who had taken antibiotics or immunosuppressive drugs, and

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nutritional supplements -especially iodine- in the past 6 months were excluded from study., r
Participants was asked about their dietary habits such as use of iodine containing salt in daily
nutrition or avoiding salt at meals. Participants who has similar dietary style was enrolled to
the study. Vegetarians or participants whom dietary style ¹ the potential of
delivering/lacking some iodine were not enrolled in the study. equired antibiotics for infective
endocarditis prophylaxis during dental procedures, or were experiencing symptoms of acute
disease were also excluded (Figure 1).

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The clinical periodontal status of participants was assessed by conducting an intraoral
examination ⁴⁴ and by referring to panoramic X-ray records. The control group (H) was defined
¹ having a probing depth (PD) of ≤ 3 mm, no clinical signs of gingival inflammation (less
than 10% of sites with bleeding upon probing and absence of gingival redness/edema), and no
radiographic evidence of alveolar crestal bone loss, and no tooth loss due to periodontitis
(each subject had at least 5 teeth for each section of jaws and 20-22 teeth in total).¹⁹

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The classification of patients with Stage III periodontitis was based on several clinical
⁴² parameters, including the presence of interdental clinical attachment level (CAL) ≥ 5 mm,
tooth loss due to periodontitis of ≤ 4 teeth (at least 5 teeth for each section of jaws and 22 teeth
for per patient), ¹⁰ PD ≥ 6 mm, vertical bone loss ≥ 3 mm, and furcation involvement of Class II
or III. This classification followed the 2017 World Workshop criteria for identifying
periodontitis.²⁰

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Blinding

The physicians who examined the individuals at the periodontology clinic divided the patients
into two groups, periodontally healthy and periodontitis, and the patients were not told which
group they belonged to before the urine samples were collected. The urine samples of the
participants were taken by the physicians, who did not know to which group ⁴ the subjects
belonged. The physicians performing the biochemical analyses did not know to which group
the participants' samples belonged. The data results were recorded and forwarded to the
author who performed the statistical analysis without mentioning the group names.

Randomization

⁴ Randomization was performed by computer-generated random number allocation. After the
diagnosis was made, the periodontitis patients and the periodontally healthy individuals were

randomly assigned (by generating a random number in the computer environment after the diagnosis was made) to the groups (Figure 1).

Collection and Storage of Urine Samples

The study participants provided spot urine samples through normal micturition at “Dentistry of XXX University, Department of Periodontology” before any surgical intervention or drug treatment. The samples were centrifuged at 2000 rpm for 5 min at 4°C. The resulting supernatant layer was collected using an automatic pipette and divided into aliquots. The samples were then stored at -80°C until the day of analysis. There was not “periods of recruitment or follow-up sessions” for taking urine samples.

Analysis of Urine Iodine Levels

The reason of measuring levels of iodine in urine is that according to World Health Organization (WHO), most iodine absorbed in the body eventually appears in the urine. Hence, the measurement of urinary iodine concentration (UIC) in casual urine specimens is recommended for monitoring iodine status. UIC is highly sensitive to recent changes in iodine intake, as up to 90% of iodine is absorbed and excreted in the urine. Therefore, urinary iodine excretion is a good marker of very recent iodine level. The increase and decrease in urine iodine level depends on renal clearance. Renal clearance of iodine is 30-50 mL plasma/min. In humans, renal clearance depends primarily on glomerular filtration, as there is no information regarding tubular secretion or active transport.^{21,22}

Urine iodine levels were measured by a spectrophotometric method using the “LTA IODIDE IN URINE (Italy)” brand kit in accordance with the manufacturer's instructions. The results found in $\mu\text{g/L}$:

Severe deficiency 0-19 $\mu\text{g/L}$

Modarete deficiency 20-49 $\mu\text{g/L}$

Media deficiency 50-99 $\mu\text{g/L}$

Optimal nutritional value 100-199 $\mu\text{g/L}$

Adequate nutritional value 200-299 $\mu\text{g/L}$

Excessive nutritional value >300 $\mu\text{g/L}$

Statistical Analyses

Sample size

For the difference (effect size: 0.71) between the two groups to be significant, the G-POWER program was used to calculate that there should be at least 33 subjects in each group at 80% power and 95% confidence level. A total of 73 subjects were included in the study, 33 of whom had periodontitis and 40 of whom had periodontitis and were healthy.

13 Statistical analyses

7
Statistical analyses were conducted using IBM SPSS 20. Descriptive statistics 38 such as the mean, standard deviation, median, minimum, maximum, percentage, and number were used to summarize the data. The 7 normal distribution of continuous variables was checked using various methods, such as the Shapiro-Wilk-W test, Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, Q-Q plot, 27 skewness, and kurtosis. To compare two independent groups, the independent-samples t-test was used if the data followed a normal distribution. Alternatively, the Mann Whitney U test was employed when normality assumptions were not met. For categorical variables analyzed in a 2 × 34 contingency table, the appropriate chi-square test was selected based on expected values: Pearson's chi-square test for expected values 46 greater than five, Yates' chi-square test for expected values 43 between three and five, and Fisher's exact test for expected values less than 4 three. To compare categorical variables greater than 2 × 2, we used the Pearson chi-square test if the expected value was greater than 5 and the Fisher-Freeman-Halton test if the expected value was less than 5. The multivariate analysis involved examining predictive risk factors between groups through logistic regression 13 analysis while considering potential risk factors previously identified. The results of the logistic regression model were expressed as odds ratios (ORs) with a 95% confidence interval. ANCOVA was employed 8 to assess the impact of cofactors on the dependent variable in multiple comparisons. ROC analysis was used to determine 8 whether the continuous variable could be used in the diagnosis. Sensitivity and specificity were calculated for the validity 19 of the diagnostic test results. In addition, the Youden index was used to determine the cutoff. Statistical significance was set at $P < 0.05$.

RESULTS

Table 1 shows that there 24 were significant differences in sex, age, and iodine levels between patients and controls ($P = 0.029$; $P < 0.001$; $P < 0.001$, respectively). After adjusting for sex and age, the 2 difference in iodine levels remained statistically significant ($P < 0.001$). The iodine levels were found to be very low in the patient group compared to the control group, and this

difference was not affected by sex or age. Table 2 indicates that there was no significant difference between sex and iodine levels among the study subjects ($P=0.073$).

We found a significant difference in urinary iodine levels between the patient and control groups ($P<0.001$). The control group's urine iodine levels were within the optimal and adequate range, whereas the patients' urine iodine levels were classified as severe-moderate deficiency (Table 3). On the other hand, the logistic regression analysis indicated that age, sex, and iodine levels were statistically significant between the patient and control groups ($P<0.001$). The analysis revealed that the patient group had lower iodine levels than the control group. Individuals with low iodine levels were 1.04 times more likely to become ill than those with high iodine levels (Table 4).

According to the results of the area under the curve (ROC) analysis, the cases of having or not having periodontitis can be defined by looking at the iodine values of the patients (0.884 ± 0.042 ; $P<0.001$). When the iodine value of individuals was below 76.93, the probability of periodontitis was 72.5%; when it was above this value, the probability of not having periodontitis was 90.9% (Figure 2, Table 5).

Periodontitis is a condition characterized by immune-inflammatory responses that arise from the accumulation of dental plaque biofilm, resulting in inflammation of the periodontal ligament and alveolar bone. Some experts suggest that a periodontal lesion can be considered a type of "wound" that requires an environment conducive to healing.²³¹

The consensus across all studies was that maintaining optimal levels of micronutrients was crucial for maintaining periodontal health. Nutritional deficiencies can negatively affect the immune response and lead to the progression of periodontal disease. Studies have found a positive correlation between lower levels of micronutrients in the serum or saliva and chronic periodontitis. Maintaining balanced levels of trace elements, including Fe, Zn, and Cu, is vital for preventing the advancement of chronic diseases such as periodontitis.⁸ Therefore, the purpose of this study was to investigate the potential effects of iodine deficiency on periodontitis.

² The findings of the present study revealed a significant reduction in urinary iodine levels among individuals with periodontitis ($P<0.001$). No prior studies have reported similar results. Previous research has predominantly relied on serum or saliva samples to measure micronutrient levels.⁸

Iodine is an essential micronutrient that depends mainly on the level of dietary iodine intake. Adequate food and micronutrient³⁵ supply is crucial for an effective and rapid immune response in inflammatory processes.⁴¹ The main dietary sources of the population for iodine are iodized salt, seafood contains iodine from seawater, and cereals from iodine-rich soils. Recurrent floods and soil erosion in mountainous regions cause iodine deficiency in the soil. Insufficient iodine in the soil causes insufficient iodine in water and food. As a result, humans and animals, whose food consumption depends entirely on the food grown in these lands, also receive insufficient iodine.²⁵ Nutritional deficiencies in certain food components can result in dental defects, oral mucosal problems, and periodontal issues in oral health.²⁶ Herein, the participants in the periodontitis group had an iodine level of 51.63 ± 4.98 , which was below the normal range (with a median deficiency of $50-99 \mu\text{g/L}$). On the other hand, the iodine level in the healthy group (160.30 ± 11.90) was within the normal range (with an optimal nutritional value of $100-199 \mu\text{g/L}$).

Iodine deficiency has a geographical distribution. Iodine deficiency affects 40% of the world's population.²⁷ Iodine deficient environment: It is characterized by soil in which the iodine has been washed away by glaciers, heavy rains or floods. This condition is frequently seen in mountainous regions such as the Himalayan region, the Andes region, and large mountain ranges in China. Iodine deficiency is also seen in Central Asia, Central Africa and Europe. When the literature is examined, it is seen that iodine deficiency in the adult population is a common condition in the geographical region where the participants of the study live.^{28,29} A study has been conducted in the same region, has found that the extent of iodine deficiency in subjects was classified as severe (15.6%), moderate (22%) and mild (26.8%).²⁸ In a study conducted in the same region evaluating the relationship between iodine deficiency and caries has been found that the iodine concentration in the urine of patient's with dental caries was lower than the urinary iodine level of healthy persons.³⁰ Our study revealed that periodontitis patients has iodine deficiency as %12,5 severe; %47,5 moderate; %27,5 mild. This situation in our participants may be due to the geographical region they live in and, accordingly, their daily dietary habits, which contain insufficient iodine.

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The findings of the present study revealed a significant reduction in urinary iodine levels among individuals with periodontitis ($P < 0.001$). No prior studies have reported similar results. Previous research has predominantly relied on serum or saliva samples to measure micronutrient levels.⁸

Its inorganic form, iodide, acts as an antioxidant by counteracting the damaging effects of hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) on human cells.^{32,25} ROS are responsible for oxidative damage and can be classified into two types: free oxygen radicals and non-radical molecules. Non-radical ROS, such as H_2O_2 , can react with cellular macromolecules, including DNA, and cause damage. ROS can cause severe DNA damage in periodontal tissue cells, leading to periodontal tissue destruction.^{26, 33} The substantial reduction in iodine levels in patients with periodontitis suggests the potential importance of iodine in maintaining periodontal health. The antioxidant properties of iodide may enable it to function as an antimicrobial agent in saliva. The presence of an H_2O_2 /peroxidase system in the salivary glands supports the idea that iodide may have a bactericidal or bacteriostatic effect.^{34,27}

Soriguer et al.^{35,28} conducted a study in which healthy volunteers were administered a diet program with a specific daily amount of iodine for six months. The researchers observed a negative correlation between urinary iodine levels and levels of CRP, an inflammation indicator, and a positive correlation with levels of glutathione peroxidase enzymes, which have an antioxidant effect. These findings support the notion that iodine has anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties. The mechanism of action of iodine is not fully understood. However, it is known to penetrate microorganisms and target specific molecules such as amino acids (including cysteine and methionine), nucleotides, and fatty acids, resulting in cell death. Iodine also has antiviral properties, but its effectiveness varies depending on the virus type. It is less effective against viruses that lack lipid envelopes and parvoviruses. Iodine may target the surface proteins of enveloped viruses and destabilize membrane fatty acids by reacting with unsaturated carbon bonds.^{36,29}

Daily intake of trace elements, including Fe, Zn, Se, Cu, iodine, and Mn, between 50 micrograms and 18 milligrams is recommended for normal body functions. In patients with chronic renal failure, their body's trace element levels may decrease due to insufficient food intake, increased dialysis, and catabolic reactions. Maintaining optimal levels of trace

elements in these patients has been shown to strengthen their immune system, reducing their susceptibility to infections and improving their quality of life. Studies suggest that the deterioration of trace element homeostasis has been linked to mortality in patients with end-stage renal disease.³⁷ Maintaining a healthy diet is essential for good health and a strong immune system, and correcting micronutrient deficiencies can be justified. There are two ways to achieve this goal: through dietary modification or administration of dietary supplements. Salt iodization is considered to be the most effective approach to combat iodine deficiency, and it is a cost-effective way to contribute to economic and social development in almost all countries. As only a small portion of the diet consists of micronutrients, it is crucial to maintain a balance, and sometimes this requires the administration of dietary supplements.³⁸ Fortified foods and supplements may be a more practical choice in cases where dietary modification is difficult. If salt iodization is not feasible, vulnerable groups may be given iodine supplements or through the use of iodophor antiseptics.^{39,40} However, there is still controversy surrounding the cost-benefit and use of multimicronutrient supplements, and this issue has yet to be resolved.⁸ Further investigation is needed to assess the efficacy of supplement administration in periodontitis patients through randomized controlled clinical trials.² Trace elements play a crucial role in regulating immune-inflammatory processes. The iodine level in the body can serve as an indicator of the ongoing destruction process in periodontitis. As only a small portion of the diet consists of micronutrients, it is crucial to maintain a balance, and sometimes this requires the administration of dietary supplements.³¹ Salt iodization is considered to be the most effective approach to combat iodine deficiency, and it is a cost-effective way to contribute to economic and social development in almost all countries. If salt iodization is not feasible, vulnerable groups may be given iodine supplements.³² Further investigation is needed to assess the efficacy of supplement administration in periodontitis patients through randomized controlled clinical trials.

STUDY LIMITATIONS

The study only examined a limited number of potential risk factors and did not take into account other factors that may contribute to the development of periodontitis, such as smoking or genetics. Another limitation is that the study only examines patients and controls from a specific geographic region, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other populations. Study population consists of Stage III periodontitis patients. From a clinical perspective, studying the amount of iodine trace elements in patients with early-stage

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periodontitis could be more interesting. Finally, the study only measured urinary iodine levels as a proxy for iodine status, which may not accurately reflect iodine levels in the body.

CONCLUSION

1. The findings of this study suggest that the iodine level in the body can serve as an indicator of the ongoing destruction process in periodontitis. The difference in average urine iodide levels can serve as a useful measure for future investigations. In addition, as a result of more extensive studies, it may be a useful biomarker for the diagnosis, prognosis and treatment plan of periodontitis.

Further investigation is needed to assess the efficacy of supplement administration in periodontitis patients through randomized controlled clinical trials.

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Figure Captions

Figure 1. Flow diagram

Figure 2. ROC curve

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